

ISic0249

I.Sicily inscription 0249

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico

Baldassare Romano

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---][hicrequi]esc[itinpace]
2. [bonememo]riae A[---anno rumplus] minus XLV [dietali]
4. [mens] A(u)g(usti) ind(ictione) XV im[p](eratore) [d(omino)n(ostro)]
5. [H]eraclio piisimopiissimo
6. s(emper) A(ugusto)

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491836

EDR 127511

EDCS 22100573

Bibliography

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Ferrua, A 1982-1983. Le iscrizioni datate della Sicilia paleocristiana. *Kokalos*. 28-29: 3-29. At 26 no.85

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